

The superbug and the personalized phage : 7 discourses they don't want you to hear !

The author : Since 2018, Christian Bois has focussed his attention on the issues of superbugs and phages. He has written a lot of articles in French to allow a clearer view on phages, phage therapy and personalized therapy necessity. His analysis and synthesis are based on the “ method for discourse ” he has developed in his PhD - 2005.

The title : We have studied pages and pages recently written about superbugs and phages. The anniversary of phage therapy in 2017 led most academic revues and information media to publish on this matter.

We discovered **big holes** in the knowledge cheese !!!

We name the holes : “ *7 discourses they don't want you to hear !* ”

Fear & dreams

Fear

Fear of dangerous bacterias - the one who attack wounds, organs or the whole bloodstream ; they are no more destroyed by antibiotics ; they are called superbugs.

Media as well as government agencies **scare** the man in the street with articles and warnings about these [superbugs](#) and how they kill and shall kill millions of people - O'Neill 2016.

They are scary because the existing antibiotics are **no more efficient**.

Dream

In 1942, phages have [won the battle](#) of Stalingrad.

In 2019, media - as well as government agencies - let people dream with stories of phages winning bacterias.

Because of the way these stories are written, we call them [phages fairy tales](#).

The contrast is great :

- in war situations, thousands of soldiers are cured
- only **a few** fairy tales are told
- the consumption of phage-based agents in Russia is more than 1 billion packs per year.

From these contradictory numbers, so some readers find fairy tales ridiculous !!!

Fear + dreams

The fairy tales would also be ridiculous in front of the amount of death - one million per year, + amputations, + invalidations. (1)

This is why media and government agencies **never tell both** in the same article or report.

Our “ speciality ” is to **tell both** = to weave discourses that are usually left separated - in different times or different places.

Twining the fairy tales - the phage success stories - and the nightmare story - superbugs threat, this method brings a great added value because it allows thinking **realistic health policies**.

Discourse about realistic health policies is absent from many papers and official reports.

Instead, they are full off extravagant discourses : weird discourse, unreal discourse, bizarre discourse, etc.

And these extravagant discourses hide the rude reality.

It looks like a HealthGate, a healthcare scandal

No media writes about it but it can be heard in the grapevine.

Two very short stories in the grapevine

First story

Paul is a French physician, his hand is infected by a superbug.

The hospital tells Paul : “ *We shall amputate your hand.* ”

Paul is amputated.

Second story - present in our [success stories list](#)

Serge gets his leg infected by the **same superbug** as Paul.

Serge travels to Tbilisi - Republic of Georgia.

Serge buys 30 euros of phages in a Georgian pharmacy.

Serge sprays the phage on his wound and drinks some of it.

Serge is cured.

Paul was amputated.

Shocking !

European people, American people can't believe that these two stories happen a **hundred times** each and every day !!!

As they can't believe it, government agencies and medias feed them with **extravagant discourses**.

We now describe the **true** picture of superbugs + phages in one page - nobody has done it so far !!!

We use a method for rhetorics - 5 Ws (2)

Superbug and personalized phage : the global discourse

[When 1]

[Bacterias invented antibiotics](#) a long, long time ago.

Bacterias learned to shield themselves from antibiotics a long, long time ago i.e. to become [superbugs](#).

[Phages](#) learned how to kill bacterias a long, long time ago.

Our method : Each and every point like this one will be compared with the extravagant discourse of some government agencies and some medias.

[By what help]

When a man is “attacked” by a superbug it is possible to save him :

- either by finding in nature the perfect phage for the superbug - case of [Tom Patterson](#)

- or by reinforcing phage power - for example by combining it with [origan du Comtat](#) .

- in few cases, a phage can be modified - see the [case of Isabelle](#)

These phages are killer phages called lytic phages.

They must not to be confused with [lysogenic phages](#) who are very different.

[Who]

Facing a patient with superbugs, the physician should act upon the ethical principles - [declaration of Helsinki](#).

Some physicians in Belgium, France, etc. say they use phage therapy within the ethical principles.

Others refer to the government authority to be allowed to use phages.

Too often, the answer is : “ *No personalized phages !* ” (3)

The patient dies, is amputated or invalidated.

One of the problems is phage cultivation.

Only a few [standard phages](#) are cultivated by a few factory plants.

[What]

There are 4 possible scenarios for a cure with phage.

Natural scenario

Phages are used as they are found in rivers, springs, etc. - see [4 paradigms](#) article.

Standard phages scenario

We saw - in the HealthGate story before - the case of Serge in Georgia.

But ... only a few [standard phages](#) are cultivated and available in Europe.

Magistral phage scenario

See :

[magistral phage](#)

Garden's hut scenario

As government agencies don't allow magistral phage therapy, there is a **clandestine** practice of phage therapy - see the hut scenario in the [4 paradigms](#) article.

[Why]

Why millions of people die, are amputated or invalidated - because of superbugs - while phage therapy is **so ancient and so simple** ?

Too many government agencies and too many medias explain it by using extravagant discourses.

We have seen that these extravagant discourses come from a confusion between [the actory paradigm and the garage paradigm](#).

[Where]

Where to find phages ?

[Gregory Resch](#) - Lausanne Switzerland - looks for phages to kill a Swiss superbug.

He gets lytic phages from Pittsburgh Pennsylvania - [Graham Hatfull](#) lab.

The American phages don't kill the Swiss superbug !!!

The phages grow where the superbug grows.

Tom Patterson's Egyptian superbug needs an Egyptian killer phage.

Navy physicians have found the proper phage ... in Maryland !!!

As bacterias, phages travel a lot !!!

[How much]

Each and every bacteria has a perfect killer phage.

Superbugs are simply “ intelligent bacterias ”.

Without a perfect killer phage a bacteria would invade the world.

In the world : There are enough killer phages to limit global bacterias' development.

Near me : The problem is for individuals who have the superbug and not the perfect phage for it.

The problem is finding a phage n° 343 for superbug n° 343.

When the matching is not possible, one may use an other way.

First by finding a cousin of phage n° 343, phage n° 344.

Second, by modifying phage n° 344 so this modified phage kills superbug n° 343.

Of course this “ phage modifying ” scenario, this “ other way ” is :

- exciting for researchers
- possibly interesting for investors

But the problem is when the “ other way ” **hides** the main road.

And this is what happens. Media and government agencies forget that, *in most cases, the right phage is at hand !*

Seven discourses about phage therapy

1. Specialists contradictory discourses

A specialist writes us :

“ So the science/lab work is to get phages / cocktails of phages that are more aggressive than their natural cousins. ”

We just saw that it is an alternative, another way when the perfect phage is not found in rivers, springs, etc.

Another expert writes to us :

“ Phage culture will never be a source of profit. It can only be a public service !”

O'Neill notes that investors quit the field of antibiotics.

Why should they enter seriously the field of standard phages **now** - the superbug problem is half a century old !!!

1 bis Toward a common sense discourse

The first specialist writes : *“ Only these phage cocktails are viable for phage therapy ! ”*

No ! These cocktails are an **other way** :

- when the perfect phage is not found
- for a strategy of [standard phages](#)

“and this is indeed what was done in the Soviet Union.”

What did they do in Soviet Union ?

They applied phages **to a lot of people** to develop their know-how !!!

There is no other way !!!

And what do American and European governments do ?

They apply phage therapy to **last-resort patients**.

When a patient is infected by a superbug, time is lost trying antibiotics that are “out of play”.

These useless antibiotics attack the immune system of the patient.

The patient suffers, may die, may be amputated or invalidated.

The **common sense** practice for developing know-how for **normal** phage therapy is to apply the phages **the day after** a superbug is identified.

2. Learning from a sad discourse !

An example of the “last resort” approach

It is the sad case of [Mallory](#) :

1. the phage killed the superbug who infected Mallory
2. Mallory was too exhausted and she died.

“By the time her doctors were able to find the phage and inject it into her lungs, it was too late. An autopsy determined, however, that the treatment had appeared to be working.” [L.A. Times](#)

3. An unreal discourse : phage therapy is NEW

A “new” therapy is a device developed in the last 3 years.

After years of clinical experience, a therapy is said to be “established”.

For example the discovery of [bacteria produced antibiotics](#) began in 1939.

In 2019, nobody would say this is a new therapy, that 80 years of research on bacteria produced antibiotics is crap.

And ... the discovery of phages and phage therapy was done [one century ago](#).

Each and every year, [more than a billion of phage doses](#) are produced and administered !!!

In 2019, what do government agencies and media say ?

They say that there is **not enough knowledge** !!!

They say that phage therapy is NEW !!!

The clear *background meaning* of this affirmation is that phage researchers and clinical physicians **produced crap for one century** !!!

This means that crap was produced in [Institut Louis Pasteur](#) - France (André Raiga-Clémenceau manual for phage therapy, etc.).

This means that crap was produced in [Eastbound countries](#) - who were able to assemble the first modular space station : MIR !!!

This means that in each and every place of the world, where people were cured by phages - Egypt, U.S.A., India, China, Australia - only crap knowledge was produced !!!

Who **can believe this unreal discourse** about phage therapy ?

Many people believe it because this discourse is served by government agencies and medias !!!

While healthcare scandals mine the credibility of agencies **they still set the tone.**

3 bis. A self contradictory discourse

In the same Ministry of health two discourses are produced.

Discourse n° 1 : “ *phages are OK !* ”

Government agency n° 1 allows phages to be sprayed on meat and fish before they enter distribution channels.

This government agency n° 1 says “ *Phages are **unable to harm humans*** ”

Discourse n° 2 : “ *phages are dangerous !* ”

Government agency n° 2 - next door - is supposed to allow phages for “ *saving the life of a dying man* ”.

N ° 2 people say “ *phage therapy **may be dangerous !*** ”.

Are phages dangerous or safe ???

They have been used [for ages](#) without any problem !!!

4. A weird discourse : there is worse than dying !

This is not directly expressed so.

But it is clearly implied in the discourse of government agencies and media.

The basic fact is that, each and every year, thousands of people are on the verge of dying from a superbug disease.

Are phages more dangerous than death ???

This is weird discourse.

5. A forgotten discourse : benefit / risk ratio

As we just saw :

- some government agencies say phages will not harm human - phages for food
- superbug put people in danger of amputation or invalidation.

Translation :

- the risk is very low - phages are safe
- the benefit is very high - stay alive with a complete body

It is **impossible** that phage therapy be more risky than amputation or invalidation !!!

Government discourse don't describe the benefit / risk ratio correctly !

A damaging discourse breach !

6. Absence of a woven discourse : the price of events

In 2016, Jim O'Neill's report evaluates **the cost** of deaths, amputations, invalidations, etc. by superbugs : tremendous, whopping, formidable !

What about the price of phage therapy ?

The basic process in the [garden's hut](#) paradigm is **cheap**.

Some useful purification may cost "something".

Useless purification may cost **more**.

Letting people die, be amputated or invalidated because of *useless purification* is a **huge problem !**

7. A missing discourse : real synergies of phages

Is there a real synergy between phages and antibiotics ?

Do antibiotics lessen the phage potential ?

What about the synergy of phages with [origan du Comtat](#) ?

Where is the knowledge repository with all the academic publications on this matter ?

Conclusion

There are some truths about phage therapy - truth established from **thousands** of years of natural phage therapy and **one century** of academic phage therapy. There is a lot of extravagant discourse : weird discourse, unreal discourse, bizarre discourse, etc.

As a consequence, **millions of people die**, are amputated or invalidated.

Tomorrow, **will government agencies and medias do better ?**

Notes

(1) Invalidation examples : loss of an eye, an ear or some guts

(2) An old method for rethorics may help us.

In the 16th century, Thomas Wilson wrote in English verse the 5 Ws:

Who, what, and where, by what helpe, and by whose :

Why, how, and when, doe many things disclose ?

When I was an engineer I learned the importance of the [5 Ws](#).

When I was a science journalist I learned the importance of the 5 Ws.

When I was a senior PhD researcher I learned the importance of the 5 Ws.

The 5 Ws are very useful for :

- constructing a discourse i.e. not forget an important dimension of the matter
- deconstructing a discourse i.e. identifying the author's forclusion / rejection of parts of reality

(3) Practices and policies about phage therapy have a high speed evolution. We write from what we observe in june 2019.

References

Foucault, Michel. The order of things - the production of discourse by researchers
O'Neill, Jim. Superbugs : an Arms Race Against Bacteria. co-written with Anthony McDonnell and Will Hall

O'Neill, Jim TACKLING DRUG-RESISTANT INFECTIONS GLOBALLY [AMR report 2016](#)